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Abstract:

This deliverable provides a detailed report on the efforts to build the Electoral Studies Knowledge Graph and the associated user interfaces in the SSHOC project. Additionally, a complete documentation of the implemented Dashboard is given.

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Executive Summary

The SSHOC project Deliverable D9.9 Delivery of User Validated Knowledge Graph and Election Studies Analytics Dashboard, describes the implementation of the SSHOC Pilot project in the field of Electoral Studies. It describes the efforts to create a domain specific Taxonomy, capable of modelling experts' knowledge in the field, in order to weave an integration layer between the various contributions on the domain of Electoral Studies. Furthermore, it describes the tools and the methods used to harvest, normalize, enrich and ingest metadata from heterogeneous sources, as part of the task to create the Electoral Studies Knowledge Graph. Finally, a documentation of the user interface, the Electoral Studies Dashboard, is provided.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
AUTNES	Austrian National Election Study
CQ	Competency Question
CQDKGC	Competency Question Driven Knowledge Graph Construction
CSV	Comma Separated Values
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative Alliance
DPU	Data Processing Unit
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
KG	Knowledge Graph
LD	Linked Data
ML	Machine Learning
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PDF	Portable Document Format
RDF	Resource Description Framework
REST	Representational State Transfer
(S)FTP	(Secure) File Transfer Protocol
SHACL	Shapes Constraint Language
SKOS	Simple Knowledge Organization System
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
SSHOC	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud
TDKGC	Test Driven Knowledge Graph Construction
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
XLS	Microsoft Excel file

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1. Introduction and Purpose of this Deliverable

Work package 9 (WP9) of SSHOC project focuses on various user communities. One of these is the user community working in the field of Electoral Studies, which is an important and highly developed field in Political Science and cognate disciplines. This user community has been defined and demarcated in the report of SSHOC Deliverable D9.6 (Demarcation Report of Electoral Studies User Community)¹.

The program of activities of WP9 includes piloting the development of infrastructural tools – known as KGs. These tools are expected to be exceptionally valuable in the development of open science; for the re-purposing and re-use of data, scientific publications, and analytical results; for promoting multidisciplinary collaboration; and to increase the potential for societal impact. In short, KGs are seen as one of the ways to realise SSHOC's aspiration of the development, realisation and maintenance of user-friendly tools & services, covering all aspects of the full research data cycle, taking into account human-centric approach and creating links between people, data, services and training.

The fundamental parameters within which this pilot KG is constructed, as well as a planning in terms of sub-tasks, and timeline have been defined in SSHOC Deliverable 9.7 – Design and Planning of a Knowledge Graph in Electoral Studies².

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide a report of the actions taken to implement the pilot Knowledge Graph on the domain of Electoral Studies and its associated dashboard interface. A user guide, and a report detailing the experiences of the developmental process, 'lessons to be learned' for the further application of KGs in and for academic user communities, and prospects for further development are provided as well.

¹ Van der Eijk, Cees. (2020). SSHOC D 9.6 Demarcation Report of Electoral Studies User Community. Zenodo. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.3725822](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3725822).

² Van der Eijk Cees, Kritzinger Sylvia, Partheymüller Julia, Kaltenböck Martin, Ahmeti Albin, & Karampatakis Sotirios. (2021). SSHOC D9.7 Design and Planning of Knowledge Graph in Electoral Studies. Zenodo. DOI [10.5281/zenodo.3824265](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3824265)

2. Ontology Development

A Knowledge Graph (KG) is a model of a knowledge domain created by subject-matter experts with the help of ML algorithms. It provides a structure and common interface for all data and enables the creation of smart multilateral relations throughout databases. Structured as an additional virtual data layer, the KG lies on top of existing databases or data sets to link all data together at scale – irrespective of whether these data are structured or unstructured.

2.1 Taxonomies Development

A taxonomy is a variety of a Knowledge Graph. It describes things that are important in a domain and the relationships between those things. In contrast, term lists are a simple knowledge model where a simple flat list of terms relevant to some domain is provided. Taxonomies on the other hand provide a more expressive knowledge model, with clearly defined relationships between concepts, in a hierarchical structure (ie parent-child or broader-narrower relations). A taxonomy is very flexible as it can grow with the needs of the use case. The more complex the information of a domain becomes the more expressive a taxonomy can become. Additional types of relationships as in a graph like structure can be defined, such as associative relationships or custom types of relationships. These characteristics of taxonomies provide advantages on end user applications. One of the advantages is that along the hierarchy of a taxonomy it is easy to aggregate information. Additionally, within a taxonomy all concepts are embedded in a context, meaning that additional information can be derived by following the concepts relations.

Figure 1. The role of a taxonomy.

A review of the existing taxonomies in the domain of Social Sciences was provided in section 5.1 of SSHOC Deliverable 9.7 [8]. However, those taxonomies are too broad and unspecific, thus cannot be used to classify

substantive content within the field of Electoral Studies. Given that, one of the largest challenges was to develop novel extensive classification schemes for the theories, concepts and research methods within the field of electoral behaviour.

In order to facilitate the goal described above, an expert-based approach was followed. Several terms composed of publication codings and variables used in studies of electoral turnout, were extracted and then structured as taxonomies. Two novel taxonomies were developed in the course of the task, namely the “Concepts & Theories” and the “Research Methods”.

2.1.1 Concepts & Theories

This taxonomy provides a classification of the different explanations of electoral turnout at the individual level (micro level) and at the macro level (aggregated level, contextual variables) narrowing down to the level of individual variables.

An initial set of terms to be structured as a taxonomy was acquired from the classifications provided in four meta-analyses [1,2,3,4]. For instance, [4] provides a set of 100 variables found in turnout models, clustered by specific concepts. Then the authors of these publications were contacted to get detailed information regarding the analyzed publications’ coding and the list of included variables. Finally, the consolidated taxonomy was further disseminated to several domain experts/scholars in the field and refined accordingly.

2.1.2 Research Methods

The taxonomy of research methods broadly divides approaches into the main (top) concepts of Research Design, Data collection and Data analysis. Besides the knowledge of the involved experts, it also relied on highly reputable publications [5, 6, 7].

2.1.3 Other Taxonomies Used

In addition to the aforementioned developed taxonomies other already established taxonomies, namely the CEESDA Topic Classification Scheme and the European Language Social Science Thesaurus (ELSST) have also been reused. Finally, a Countries taxonomy was used. This taxonomy is structured in three levels of granularity namely continents, regions and countries.

2.2 Electoral Studies Ontology

Apart from the taxonomies in use, the Electoral Studies Knowledge Graph is composed of several other types of instances such as Publications, Population Surveys and Authors to name a few. In this case a taxonomy is not expressive enough to describe those instances and the relationships between them effectively. Additionally, instances are not in a hierarchical structure. Thus, a custom ontology was developed, based on three requirements:

1. Provide proper classes and properties to describe the models to be represented on the KG

3. Specification of Resources to be Covered by the Pilot-KG

The domain-specific resources to be covered by the pilot Electoral Studies KG was described in Section 3 of D9.7[8]. This includes the following:

- professionally curated **empirical data**. These are structured survey datasets, although they may, occasionally, also be in less structured form such as (transcripts of) unstructured interviews, other unstructured textual data, etc.
- scholarly **publications** on electoral participation. These consist mainly of books and book chapters, published articles, and publications in the so-called 'grey' literature (conference papers, reports that are not published in book or article form).
- **scholars** actively involved in the domain of the pilot-KG. Those are extracted from the various publications metadata.
- **elections** that are described or analysed by publications, or about which relevant data is available in empirical data.
- **theories; concepts** and their operationalisation in the form of variables; and analytical approaches and methods that are used in publications as described in Section 2.1.

In this section the resources that were actually used for the realisation of the Electoral Studies Knowledge Graph are described.

3.1 Datasets

In the domain of Electoral Studies, the core of relevant datasets are the voter surveys produced by national election studies. However, there is a lot of variation across countries and over time in terms of methodology followed and consistency. In some countries elections have been systematically monitored over several decades, while in other countries voter data is rather scarce or non-existent.

In the scope of the pilot-KG two main sources of metadata were considered, namely the CEESDA Data Catalogue³ and Datacite⁴. CEESDA DC API offers rich metadata regarding surveys, providing explicit methodology information.

³ CEESDA Data Catalogue: <https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/> [accessed 01.04.2021]

⁴ DATACITE: <https://datacite.org/> [accessed 01.04.2021]

Figure 3. Sample methodology metadata provided by the CEESDA Data Catalogue. Screen Capture.

As is depicted in Fig. 3, there are several properties describing the methodology followed for a specific survey. Terminology used is generally based on DDI controlled vocabularies. However, this level of richness is not always available. Additionally, metadata for a considerable number of national election study programs were not available.

On the other hand, Datacite's API provides basic metadata describing surveys. Information about titles, abstracts, DOIs are usually available. Additionally, in some cases classification based on generic classification schemes like CEESDA Topic Classification is provided, along with free text descriptions of methodologies used and relevant dates (collection periods etc).

Given that Datacite offers a broader coverage on national election study programmes than the CEESDA catalogue a decision was made to use the former for the initial population of the pilot-KG. It is foreseen that additional metadata originating from the CEESDA Data Catalogue and other relevant sources will be used in order to further enrich the KG on a later stage. An overview of the national election study programmes that were retrievable from Datacite, along with the queries used for retrieval is given in [APPENDIX B](#).

3.2 Publications

Relevant types of publications can include books, book chapters, journal articles, as well as conference paper and pre-prints. In a first step, important publications were identified by collecting the publications referenced in four meta-analyses [1, 2, 3, 4]. The authors of these papers were contacted to get detailed lists of references. However, the metadata of the publications referenced in the meta-analyses were in varying formats and could

not be easily enriched. Thus, in a first step, the Scopus abstract and citation database was used, by utilizing the Scopus API through the R package *rscopus*⁵, to search for all articles with the information available from the meta-analyses⁶. Through this the associated DOIs of the initial set of publications were acquired, a total of 344 items. However, manual editing of the results was still needed because a set of search results was referring to irrelevant publications. After the manual corrections it was possible to retrieve up-to-date and additional metadata.

3.2.1 Searching for More Publications

To extend the set of publications, the Scopus and Microsoft Academic APIs were used to search for relevant publications. For the Microsoft Academic API the R package *microdemic*⁷ was used. The following search queries were used:

- Scopus API:

- Query:

```
TITLE-ABS-KEY("voter turnout" OR "electoral turnout" OR "electoral participation" OR "voter participation" OR "turnout in election" OR "election turnout")
```

- Description: This meant that publications were included if one of the terms was included in either the title, the abstract, or the keywords.

- Microsoft Academic API:

- Query:

```
Or(And(W='voter',W='turnout'),And(W='electoral',W='turnout'),And(W='electoral',W='participation'),And(W='voter',W='participation'),And(W='election',W='turnout'),And(AW='voter',AW='turnout',AW='election',AW='participation'),Composite(F.FN='voter turnout'))
```

- Description: This meant that one of the following had to apply:

- Title had to include: (voter AND turnout) OR (electoral AND turnout) OR (electoral AND participation) OR (voter AND participation) OR (election AND turnout)
 - Abstract had to include: (voter AND turnout AND election AND participation)
 - Category had to be: voter turnout

In both cases only results where a unique DOI was present were kept.

⁵ <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/rscopus/> [accessed 04.04.2021]

⁶ Scopus preview: <https://www.scopus.com/search/form.uri#basic> [accessed 04.04.2021]

⁷ <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/microdemic/> [accessed 04.04.2021]

3.2.2 Updating and Gathering More Metadata

Having the DOI for all publications, enabled us to retrieve more information on publications. Two different sources were used to retrieve useful metadata, namely Scopus and Crossref (by using R packages *rscopus* and *rcrossref*). Additionally, the R package *fulltext* was used to get access to the abstracts of articles through various APIs (Crossref, Scopus, SemanticScholar). Abstracts had to be sanitized from irrelevant text (see [APPENDIX C](#) for a detailed description). Finally, all metadata harvested from the various sources were consolidated into a single CSV file in order to proceed with mapping and ingestion into the Electoral Studies Knowledge Graph. For a detailed description of the retrieved fields see [APPENDIX D](#). Following the expansion of the initial seed set retrieved from the meta-analyses, a total of 3866 publications were identified in order to ingest.

3.3 Integrating Data Sources

The software component that is used for the pilot project is PoolParty Semantic Suite. PoolParty is a semantic middleware that enriches and contextualizes data with relevant information. The platform links and integrates different datasets by applying semantic knowledge models. PoolParty Semantic Suite uses the SKOS⁸—Simple Knowledge Organization System—vocabulary to structure and describe the knowledge model. SKOS provides a model for expressing the basic structure and content of concept schemes such as thesauri, classification schemes, subject heading lists, taxonomies, folksonomies, and other similar types of controlled vocabulary. As an application of the Resource Description Framework (RDF), SKOS allows concepts (elements of a taxonomy) to be composed and published on the World Wide Web, linked with data on the Web and integrated into other concept schemes⁹. It was developed within the W3C standards framework. RDF uses graphs as its data structure. This means that each resource is a node and edges connect these nodes. A set of two nodes connected through an edge is called a triple. Multiple triples can be combined to create a graph¹⁰. The edges are called 'properties' in RDF. They can also connect a node with a literal, in the case of SKOS these are the labels, definitions or scope notes.

The image below displays data of a thesaurus presented as a graph. The graph has the concept 'Australian Open' as its central node. Several edges connect this node to its labels and definition as well as to other nodes. All edges are typed, thereby indicating which kind of relationships exist between the nodes they connect, e.g. the node 'Australian Open' is connected to the node 'Australian Open men's singles' via `skos:narrower`.

⁸ <http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/> [accessed 01.04.2021]

⁹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/2009/NOTE-skos-primer-20090818/> [accessed 01.04.2021]

¹⁰ <https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf11-primer/> [accessed 01.04.2021]

Figure 4. A part of a taxonomy. Describing the "Australian Open" using the SKOS model.

Thus, in order to work with PoolParty, data has to be transformed into RDF. Different connectors in PoolParty Semantic Suite are capable of ingesting data, and afterwards use that data in conjunction with the existing one. For instance, in PoolParty one can ingest RDF data via Excel import, RDF import, or APIs, hence creating a new or refining the existing taxonomy. Additionally, in PoolParty's UnifiedViews component, one can download CSV, XLS or RDF data from an (S)FTP location on a server, consume an API, ingest data from a SPARQL endpoint etc, transform them into an RDF model suitable for the use case and load them into PoolParty Semantic Suite, or some generic RDF datastore (a triplestore), to be accessed by end user applications. All these functionalities are possible due to availability of DPUs capable of doing the respective tasks by encapsulating the bespoke logic.

The data and information sources specified in subsection 3.1 and 3.2 were harvested by developing two data ingestion pipelines in the UnifiedViews component of PoolParty Semantic Suite that allows fully automated data acquisition, cleaning, harmonization and publishing from specified sources. Once the ingestion pipeline is defined, data and information can be harvested continuously and will be mapped and ingested to enrich and update the KG. Each of the UnifiedViews pipelines is composed of several DPUs that execute a specific process. Each DPU specifies zero or more input channels that are used to provide input data for the specific DPU. Additionally, each DPU specifies zero or more output channels that can be used to transfer data to another DPU for further processing. This mechanism allows the chaining of several DPUs in order to form a processing pipeline using the DPUs as the building blocks.

RML Schema Mapping DPU

The RDF Mapping language (RML)[9] is a generic scalable mapping language defined to express rules that map data in heterogeneous structures and serializations to an RDF data model. RML deals with the mapping definitions in a uniform, modular, interoperable and extensible fashion. RML is defined as a superset of the W3C-recommended mapping language, R2RML, that maps data in relational databases to RDF. In RML, the mapping of data to the RDF data model is based on one or more Triples Maps that define how the triples will be generated.

The RML Schema Mapping DPU that UnifiedViews provides, is used to define descriptive and reusable mappings in the RML specification. It wraps the CARML¹¹ mapping engine, a Java library that transforms structured sources to RDF based as declared in a RML mapping, in accordance with the RML spec. Besides mapping, custom functions can be defined in order to extend the capabilities of the engine during mapping such as data cleaning or data enrichment. It is the core DPU of both pipelines developed in the course of the construction of the Electoral Studies Knowledge Graph.

3.3.1 Harvesting Metadata

Here a description of the pipeline developed to harvest metadata regarding Electoral Studies datasets is given. As described in subsection 3.1, Datacite.org was used for this initial population of the KG with metadata about Datasets regarding Election Studies. Datacite’s API offers the capability to query its content either by specifying individual fields based on the properties of the entities or/and full-text search on specific fields. A UnifiedViews pipeline was developed in order to harvest the resources from Datacite. The first building block of the pipeline is the Files Download DPU. This is where one can specify the queries for the Datacite API as defined in APPENDIX B. This DPU uses the HTTP protocol to query the source, stores the results in the working environment and forwards them to the next DPU, which is the RML Schema Mapping DPU.

Figure 5. The Datacite.org pipeline in UnifiedViews

The RML Schema Mapping DPU is responsible for three tasks:

¹¹ <https://github.com/carm1/carm1> [accessed 01.04.2021]

- Extraction and transformation of core entities found in the raw data; that is information about Authors (name, identifier) and Datasets (title, abstract, dates, DOI etc) using the developed Electoral Studies Ontology
- Annotate and interlink dataset metadata with the developed taxonomies using the PoolParty Extractor API
- Cleaning and normalization of the input data.

After the mapping process is completed, the output RDF graph is validated using the RDF4j SHACL DPU. This DPU validates RDF graphs based on constraints defined using the Shapes Constraint Language (SHACL)¹². A snippet of the implemented shapes is given in [APPENDIX G](#). The validation report is then stored on the internal triplestore. A decision was made to use the reports as a quality check indicator. This means that ingestion will not fail if there are critical errors, and the KG will be stored on the triplestore in any case. But administrative users can view the validation results and edit erroneous resources after ingestion in a continuous effort to further improve the Knowledge Graph. For instance, in case some resource is missing a title or an abstract property in English, this would be reported as a violation. Finally, the output RDF graph is uploaded to a triplestore, so that users can access and query it. In this phase of the pilot, the triplestore can be accessed only by administrative users, but it is foreseen that public read-only access will be provided by the end of the project.

The publications pipeline follows the same architecture as the datasets pipeline architecture. The only difference is the initial input, which is currently a remote CSV file as described in section 3.2.

¹² <https://www.w3.org/TR/shacl/> [accessed 01.04.2021]

4. User Interface Development and Implementation

In the planning delivered in D9.7 a set of user stories was reported to set up an initial pool for requirements elicitation. Additionally, user involvement in the form of workshops and brainstorming sessions targeting the potential end-users was considered. However, these plans were hampered by the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic; a large number of the targeted events were cancelled, postponed or realized as online events. Thus, the expected input from actual users of the Electoral Studies Dashboard was limited to the valuable input from the domain experts participating in Task 9.3, as well as some input from external stakeholders that the pilot team was in touch during this time. Several internal meetups were held, presenting various use cases to provide ideas of what is possible and to identify what would be useful for the implementation of the dashboard. The aim was to provide a functional prototype that can be further extended with additional functionalities till the end of the project.

4.1 Requirements for the User Interface

The following table summarizes the requirements for the user interface. These are grouped into five basic categories and prioritized using the MoSCoW method.

Table 1. User Interfaces requirements. (M=MUST, S=SHOULD, C=COULD, W=WONT)

ID	Description	Priority
Faceted Search		
FAC-01	Filtering of results based on the data model	M
FAC-02	Filtering of results based on taxonomies	M
FAC-03	Selection of multiple facets	M
FAC-04	Unselect specific facet	M
FAC-05	Reset all filters button	M
FAC-06	Hierarchical view on filter values	S
FAC-07	Click on filter value to select a facet	M
FAC-08	Search on facet values	M
FAC-09	Autocomplete on search field of filter values	S
FAC-10	User configurable switch between tree view and list view on the facets panel	S

FAC-11	Administrators can modify the size of the facet values presented on the sidebar to a maximum value.	C
FAC-12	Users can fold/expand specific filters on the side bar.	C
Information Display		
INFO-01	Retrieve full description of a resource	M
INFO-02	Display title and description of a resource on search results	M
INFO-03	Associate different type of resources with descriptive icons (journal, dataset, book etc)	C
INFO-04	Display aggregated information in charts	S
INFO-05	Adjust ordering on x-axis on the charts(alphabetical, frequency, chronological)	C
INFO-06	Adjust ordering on search results by year	C
INFO-07	Adjust ordering on search results by relevance	C
INFO-08	Histogram displaying publications by publication year	M
INFO-09	Histogram displaying the most frequent authors	M
Full Text search capabilities		
FTS-01	Full-text search on titles	M
FTS-02	Full-text search on abstracts	M
Integration Capabilities		
INT-01	Provide an HTTP API to query the resources	C
INT-02	Export search results in tabular format	S
User friendliness		
UF-01	Paginated results	M
UF-02	Ability to change the size of pagination	S
UF-03	Pagination controls	M
UF-04	Toggable facets panel	C

UF-05	Resizable charts and search results panels	C
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Requirements noted in **GREEN** are already implemented. After the release of the prototype, the SSHOC Electoral Studies Pilot partners intend to reach out to a broader audience to further extend this initial set of requirements.

4.2 Implementation

PoolParty offers GraphSearch, a faceted search application making it possible to provide insight into tagged documents and knowledge graphs, using the provided default graphical user interface or the GraphSearch API.

System administrators can configure it with a couple of clicks after the set up your PoolParty thesaurus and custom schemes. Thus, the GraphSearch interface lets end users quickly explore data in a ready-to-use search application. It also helps to check on the validity of the created knowledge graph, the thesauri, and custom schemes since the faceted search and the results are displayed based on them.

Additionally to the user interface, PoolParty GraphSearch offers an HTTP API. Using the API allows integration of PoolParty GraphSearch into other existing search applications or to build a custom search interface on top.

4.3 User Guide

This section contains a short guide on how to access the Electoral Studies Dashboard, available under:

<https://sshoc.poolparty.biz/GraphSearch>

Detailed documentation of how to use the GraphSearch API and Admin Dashboard is given on the official PoolParty Documentation Portal¹³. Here a documentation of the GraphSearch Interface elements and their functions from the end-user perspective is provided.

4.3.1 Interface Menu Elements

In Figure 6 you see the elements of the default PoolParty GraphSearch graphical user interface when you first access it, showing a Search Space that has already been configured, search results in list view and an active facet filter. These are described in detail in the Table 2.

¹³ <https://help.poolparty.biz/pp/user-guide-for-knowledge-engineers/semantic-integrator-features/the-poolparty-graphsearch-overview> [accessed 01.04.2021]

Figure 6. The interface of the Electoral Studies Dashboard. Screen Capture.

Table 2. The elements of the Dashboard

Element	No. in the Image	Description
Facets Pane	1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The available facets are based on the concept schemes of the PoolParty project configured for the Search Space. Additionally, the selection of individual Facets in the pane is possible. Click the Gear icon to expand a pane to select facets.
Search	2	<p>Search across the data by relations (facets) as well as full-text is available. The search offers autocomplete.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Example: Looking up a term like 'Electoral laws' would result in the list of results that are related to that term.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Each result is associated with some context: this can be either a specific facet (a property) if any matched or you can use the full-text context to search for this term in several properties ● In the drop down beside the search field you can change the search language. Available languages here depend on the language configured in the custom scheme used for the Search Space.
Display Settings - Export Search Results - User Settings icons	3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Change Display Settings so you can also hide search results. ● Export Search Results as an Excel file. ● The User Settings icon which lets you access the Admin Dashboard, the GraphSearch API and contains the option to log out.
Filter Bar	4	The Filter Bar will display the facet filters you selected, if any, and the Clear Filters button. Clicking on the 'X' icon next to a specific filter will clear this specific filter. Click on the Clear Filters button will clear all filters.
Search Result Pane - Switch Views: Grid, List, Details	5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Four icons in the top-right hand corner, three of them offering similar functions to window controls (minimize, maximize, close). ● The fourth icon lets you change the result views, three modes are available: Grid view, List view and Details view.
Pagination Controls	6	At the bottom of the search results pane you find the pagination controls. You can configure the number of results per page, or select a particular page to jump to.
Search Results - List Item - Document Options Menu	7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Hover your mouse over the row's end of an entry to bring up the Document Options Menu. Click it to open a detailed information view for that list item. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If you configured a recommender and /or similarity plugin, you will see their search results in that dialogue too.

4.3.2 Charts in the Interface

System Administrators can also configure Visualization charts (pie, column and column 2D) for your data, and if your Search Space is set up accordingly, you will see them in the top area of the interface (1 in Figure 7).

You can open the above-mentioned detailed view of a search result item here as well, by clicking its image or tile, if no image is available (2). For the case of the Electoral Studies KG Dashboard, there are currently two different charts on the top of the Results View panel. On the left chart you can see the number of publications per year, while on the right chart there are the most frequent authors. The graphs are interactive, meaning that the selected facets affect the results displayed in the graphs.

Figure 7. Charts in the Dashboard. Screen Capture.

4.3.3 Results View and the Details View

Results can be presented in three different modes:

- List view
- Table view
- Grid view

The default presentation is in a List View. To cycle through the different options you can click on the Toggle View Mode button (1).

You can access the view for any search result item in two ways:

- In the List view of the results, hover over the title of a result. The Document Options menu will be displayed (noted by three vertical dots). Click on it to display the Show details button (2) and click it for the Details View.
- In the Grid View, click the result tile to get the Details View (3).

On the Details View you can get a full description of the selected entity. A complete description of the Details View is provided below.

AUTNES Candidate Survey 2008

← → AUTNES Candidate Survey 2... (1)

DESCRIPTION (2)

The AUTNES Candidate Survey 2008 was conducted after the Austrian national parliamentary election of 28 September 2008. The dataset is based on a written census survey of the 4,081 candidates for the National Council election. Candidates were asked questions on four topics: Political background and activities, campaigning, issues and policies as well as democracy and representation. The first subject area contains variables like the candidates' party affiliation, its duration and possible changes as well as several indicators for political activity like association membership or the average weekly time spent with party activities. Next, candidates were asked about several details of their campaign: Its aim and strategy, time spent, occurring problems, communication means, personal campaign funds and relationship with the party. The third section on issues and policies also includes (besides questions about the candidates' positions on several topics) coalition preferences, left-right self-placement and opinions on EU topics. The final part of the dataset holds information on candidates' general attitudes about democracy, their preferred electoral system as well as their understanding of how a Member of Parliament should act.

AUTHOR (3)

- Müller, Wolfgang C.
- Eder, Nikolaus
- Jenny, Marcelo

ENTITY TYPES

- Dataset

5 Recommended No recommendations available

4 See Also Graph Similarity

ANES 2000 ... ANES 2000 ... ANES 2000 ... ANES 2000 ... ANES 2000 ...

6 Similarities: 5

CLOSE

Figure 8. Details of a resource. Screen Capture.

Table 3. Elements of the Details Dialogue of a resource

Element	No. in the Image	Description
Resource Title	1	The title of the resource
Description field	2	The description that is part of this item's data, also visible in the item's Details View of the project used for this Search Space . This is the abstract of the resource, when this is available.
Property entries	3	A list of properties used in this Search Space . They are determined by relations of the respective custom scheme. You can expand them by using the Arrow icon behind each property's entry.
See Also	4	If a similarity plugin has been configured for the Search Space , further items similar to the current resource are displayed here.
Recommended	5	Recommender results. If you configured a recommender plugin for this Search Space , its results will be visible here. In this case no plugin is present.
Similarities	6	Determine the number of similar items by clicking the arrow and selecting a predefined number from the menu.

5. Testing

Creating a knowledge graph is an iterative process - as described in Deliverable 9.7 - that involves many stakeholders and experts in a particular domain. Despite the KG undergoing different phases as described in Linked Data Lifecycle, as well as many iterations, it still might be incomplete. In fact, one should set up infrastructure and workflows so that KG can be updated continuously, both by humans and machines. Hence, when ingesting data from multiple sources, it is often the case that the resulting data despite being homogenized, is still inconsistent and incomplete. In order to test the validity of the knowledge graph - as described in D9.7 - it is needed to:

- (i) formulate different (SPARQL) queries or (SHACL) shapes (see [APPENDIX G](#)) in order to check if the data in KG is complete, in the sense that a set of obligatory properties exist for each item, and adheres to the specified structure;
- (ii) ask experts to try to formulate queries using the dashboard and see if their intention is captured by the expressivity provided by the dashboard.

The expressivity offered by the dashboard captures very complex queries that are formed in an AND conjunction as the user picks different values from a facet. The user is then able to retrieve very specific information that is constrained by the values picked from the interface. These facet values come from different parts of the taxonomy or ontology. On top of that, different visualisations as in pie or bar charts also help to have a better understanding of the search results.

The dashboard was given to scientists in the domain of election studies in order to validate the search results. The feedback has been positive, where they have been able to create queries which has not been able to do previously without the help of a KG. They were able to write queries like:

"Give me all Publications from author Donald P Green that have to do with Electoral behavior published in year 2010 and that use Quantitative data collection as Research methods"

To answer this query is now possible thanks to the underlying KG that consists of relevant data from multiple sources, as described in Sec 3. Basic statistics about the KG are provided in [APPENDIX E](#).

Some insights about the KG are given on table 4 - the results are retrieved from a set of SPARQL queries.

Table 4. Insights of the KG

Class	Count	Note
sshoc:Publication	3865	Publications of various types (journal articles, book chapters etc)
sshoc:Dataset	1082	Electoral behavior surveys/datasets or other relevant datasets
sshoc:Author	5303	Number of Authors
skos:Concept	5510	Total number of Concepts on the taxonomies developed/used
sshoc:PublicationName	1422	Name of the publication (Journal name etc.)
sshoc:Publisher	347	Publishers of the publications
sshoc:Keyword	4669	Keywords mentioned in publications.

Conclusion

In this deliverable we presented the efforts to create the pilot Knowledge Graph on the domain of Electoral Studies. We presented the efforts to harvest, integrate, interlink and analyse metadata from national, European and cross-national electoral behaviour datasets and relevant publications through implementing sustainable and on-demand mechanisms based on the Linked Data principles and the Semantic Web Technologies. Additionally, we presented the implementation of a user interface, the Electoral Studies Dashboard, which is the entry point for end users of the Knowledge Graph. The main features of the Dashboard are described in detail, providing a complete user documentation.

In the remainder of this task and till the end of the project, a considerable effort will be made to raising awareness about the Knowledge Graph on Electoral Studies and its Dashboard, providing training and involving members of the user community in the pilot, in a crowd contributing fashion.

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APPENDIX A. *The Electoral Studies Ontology*

```

@prefix :      <https://sshoc.poolparty.biz/SSHOC/> .
@prefix rdf:   <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#> .
@prefix rdfs:  <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> .
@prefix owl: <http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#> .
@prefix xsd:   <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> .
@prefix skos:  <http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#> .
@prefix dc:    <http://purl.org/dc/terms/> .
@base         <https://sshoc.poolparty.biz/SSHOC/> .

:
  rdf:type      owl:Ontology ;
  dc:title      "Electoral Studies Ontology"@en ;
  dc:description "Electoral Studies Ontology"@en .
#####

### Property Definitions (Number of Property) 26 ###
# ----- Property 0-----

:abstract
  rdf:type      owl:DatatypeProperty ;
  rdfs:label    "abstract"@en ;
  rdfs:domain   :Resource ;
  rdfs:range    rdf:langString .
# ----- Property 1-----

:publicationYear
  rdf:type      owl:DatatypeProperty ;
  rdfs:label    "Publication Year"@en ;
  rdfs:domain   :Resource ;
  rdfs:range    xsd:string .
# ----- Property 2-----

:issue
  rdf:type      owl:DatatypeProperty ;
  rdfs:label    "issue"@en ;
  rdfs:domain   :Publication ;
  rdfs:range    rdfs:Literal .
# ----- Property 3-----

:timeMethod
  rdf:type      owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label    "timeMethod"@en ;
  rdfs:domain   :PopulationSurvey ;
  rdfs:range    :TimeMethod .
# ----- Property 4-----

:unitType
  rdf:type      owl:ObjectProperty ;

```

```
    rdfs:label "unitType"@en ;
    rdfs:domain :PopulationSurvey ;
    rdfs:range :UnitType .
# ----- Property 5-----

:mentionsCountry
  rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label "mentionsCountry"@en ;
  rdfs:domain :Resource ;
  rdfs:range skos:Concept .
# ----- Property 6-----

:dataCollectionYear
  rdf:type owl:DatatypeProperty ;
  rdfs:label "dataCollectionYear"@en ;
  rdfs:domain :PopulationSurvey ;
  rdfs:range rdfs:Datatype .
# ----- Property 7-----

:freeTextSamplingProcedure
  rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label "freeTextSamplingProcedure"@en ;
  rdfs:domain :PopulationSurvey ;
  rdfs:range :FreeTextSamplingProcedure .
# ----- Property 8-----

:keyword
  rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label "Keyword"@en ;
  rdfs:domain :Resource ;
  rdfs:range skos:Concept .
# ----- Property 9-----

:pages
  rdf:type owl:DatatypeProperty ;
  rdfs:label "pages"@en ;
  rdfs:domain :Resource ;
  rdfs:range rdfs:Literal .
# ----- Property 10-----

:publicationDate
  rdf:type owl:DatatypeProperty ;
  rdfs:label "publicationDate"@en ;
  rdfs:domain :Resource ;
  rdfs:range xsd:string .
# ----- Property 11-----

:publication
  rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label "Publication Name"@en ;
  rdfs:domain :Publication ;
  rdfs:range skos:Concept .
```

```
# ----- Property 12-----
:url
  rdf:type    owl:DatatypeProperty, owl:FunctionalProperty ;
  rdfs:label  "url"@en ;
  rdfs:domain :PopulationSurvey ;
  rdfs:range  xsd:string .
# ----- Property 13-----
:classification
  rdf:type    owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label  "classification"@en ;
  rdfs:domain :Resource ;
  rdfs:range  skos:Concept .
# ----- Property 14-----
:studyArea
  rdf:type    owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label  "Study Area"@en ;
  rdfs:domain :Resource ;
  rdfs:range  :GeographicalArea .
# ----- Property 15-----
:dataCollectionPeriodStartdate
  rdf:type    owl:DatatypeProperty, owl:FunctionalProperty ;
  rdfs:label  "dataCollectionPeriodStartdate"@en ;
  rdfs:domain :PopulationSurvey ;
  rdfs:range  xsd:date .
# ----- Property 16-----
:modeOfCollection
  rdf:type    owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label  "modeOfCollection"@en ;
  rdfs:domain :PopulationSurvey ;
  rdfs:range  :ModeOfCollection .
# ----- Property 17-----
:xmlSourceUrl
  rdf:type    owl:DatatypeProperty, owl:FunctionalProperty ;
  rdfs:label  "xmlSourceUrl"@en ;
  rdfs:domain :PopulationSurvey ;
  rdfs:range  xsd:string .
# ----- Property 18-----
:publisher
  rdf:type    owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label  "Publisher"@en ;
  rdfs:domain :Resource ;
  rdfs:range  :Publisher .
# ----- Property 19-----
:citations
```

```

    rdf:type    owl:DatatypeProperty ;
    rdfs:label  "citations"@en ;
    rdfs:domain :Resource ;
    rdfs:range  rdfs:Literal .
# ----- Property 20-----

:dataCollectionPeriodEnddate
    rdf:type    owl:DatatypeProperty, owl:FunctionalProperty ;
    rdfs:label  "dataCollectionPeriodEnddate"@en ;
    rdfs:domain :PopulationSurvey ;
    rdfs:range  xsd:date .
# ----- Property 21-----

:volume
    rdf:type    owl:DatatypeProperty ;
    rdfs:label  "volume"@en ;
    rdfs:domain :Publication ;
    rdfs:range  rdfs:Literal .
# ----- Property 22-----

:doi
    rdf:type    owl:DatatypeProperty, owl:FunctionalProperty ;
    rdfs:label  "doi"@en ;
    rdfs:domain :Resource ;
    rdfs:range  xsd:string .
# ----- Property 23-----

:hasConcept
    rdf:type    owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label  "hasConcept"@en ;
    rdfs:domain :Resource ;
    rdfs:range  skos:Concept .
# ----- Property 24-----

:hasAuthor
    rdf:type    owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label  "Author"@en ;
    rdfs:domain :Resource ;
    rdfs:range  :Author .
# ----- Property 25-----

:hasAuthored
    rdf:type    owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label  "hasAuthored"@en ;
    rdfs:domain :Author ;
    rdfs:range  :Resource .

### Class Definitions (Number of Classes) 24 ###
# ----- Class 0-----

skos:Concept

```

```
    rdf:type    owl:Class ;
    rdfs:label  "Concept"@IRI-based .
# ----- Class 1-----

:PopulationSurvey
    rdf:type    owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf  :Dataset ;
    rdfs:label    "Population Survey"@en .
# ----- Class 2-----

:ModeOfCollection
    rdf:type    owl:Class ;
    rdfs:label  "ModeOfCollection"@IRI-based ;
    rdfs:label  "ModeOfCollection"@en .
# ----- Class 3-----

:FreeTextSamplingProcedure
    rdf:type    owl:Class ;
    rdfs:label  "FreeTextSamplingProcedure"@en .
# ----- Class 4-----

:Author
    rdf:type    owl:Class ;
    rdfs:label  "Author"@en .
# ----- Class 5-----

:GeographicalArea
    rdf:type    owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf  skos:Concept ;
    rdfs:label    "GeographicalArea"@en .
# ----- Class 6-----

:UnitType
    rdf:type    owl:Class ;
    rdfs:label  "UnitType"@en .
# ----- Class 7-----

:Publisher
    rdf:type    owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf  skos:Concept ;
    rdfs:label    "Publisher"@en .
# ----- Class 8-----

:Publication
    rdf:type    owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf  :Resource ;
    rdfs:label    "Publication"@en .
# ----- Class 9-----

:TimeMethod
    rdf:type    owl:Class ;
    rdfs:label  "TimeMethod"@en .
```

```
# ----- Class 10-----  
  
:Resource  
  rdf:type    owl:Class ;  
  rdfs:label  "Resource"@en .  
# ----- Class 11-----  
  
:Dataset  
  rdf:type          owl:Class ;  
  rdfs:subClassOf  :Resource ;  
  rdfs:label       "Dataset"@en .  
# ----- Class 12-----  
  
:BookChapter  
  rdf:type          owl:Class ;  
  rdfs:subClassOf  :Publication ;  
  rdfs:label       "Book Chapter"@en .  
# ----- Class 13-----  
  
:ConferencePaper  
  rdf:type          owl:Class ;  
  rdfs:subClassOf  :Publication ;  
  rdfs:label       "Conference Paper"@en .  
# ----- Class 14-----  
  
:EditedVolume  
  rdf:type          owl:Class ;  
  rdfs:subClassOf  :Publication ;  
  rdfs:label       "Edited Volume"@en .  
# ----- Class 15-----  
  
:JournalArticle  
  rdf:type          owl:Class ;  
  rdfs:subClassOf  :Publication ;  
  rdfs:label       "Journal Article"@en .  
# ----- Class 16-----  
  
:Monograph  
  rdf:type          owl:Class ;  
  rdfs:subClassOf  :Publication ;  
  rdfs:label       "Monograph"@en .  
# ----- Class 17-----  
  
:Other  
  rdf:type          owl:Class ;  
  rdfs:subClassOf  :Publication ;  
  rdfs:label       "Other"@en .  
# ----- Class 18-----  
  
:Report  
  rdf:type          owl:Class ;  
  rdfs:subClassOf  :Publication ;
```

```
    rdfs:label      "Report"@en .
# ----- Class 19-----

:Thesis
  rdf:type          owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf  :Publication ;
  rdfs:label       "Thesis"@en .
# ----- Class 20-----

:WorkingPaper
  rdf:type          owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf  :Publication ;
  rdfs:label       "Working Paper"@en .
# ----- Class 21-----

:OtherDataset
  rdf:type          owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf  :Dataset ;
  rdfs:label       "Other Dataset"@en .
# ----- Class 22-----

:OtherPopulationSurvey
  rdf:type          owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf  :PopulationSurvey ;
  rdfs:label       "Other Population Survey"@en .
# ----- Class 23-----

:NationalElectionStudy
  rdf:type          owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf  :PopulationSurvey ;
  rdfs:label       "National Election Study"@en .
```

APPENDIX B. An overview of the National Election Study programmes covered by the current KG and the queries used to retrieve relevant metadata.

National election study program	Since	Data provider	Query	Number of items
Australian Election Study (AES)	1987	Australian Data Archive (ADA)	https://api.datacite.org/doi?query=australian+electio n+studies&resource-type-id=dataset&page[size]=1000	19
Austrian National Election Study (AUTNES)	2008	Austrian Social Science Data Archive (AUSSDA)	https://api.datacite.org/doi?query=titles.title%3A+AU TNES+AND+publisher%3A+AUSSDA+OR+publisher %3A+GESIS&page[size]=1000	52
Belgian National Election Study (BNES)	1991	Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS)	https://api.datacite.org/doi?query=titles.title%3A+%2 8Belgium+OR+BELGIAN%29+AND+%22General+El ection+Study%22+AND+publisher%3A+DANS&page [size]=1000	6
Canadian Election Study (CES)	1965	Canadian Opinion Research Archive (CORA)	https://api.datacite.org/doi?query=container.title%3A +%22Canadian+National+Elections+Study+%28CNE S%29+Series%22+AND+publisher%3A+ICPSR&pag e[size]=1000	24
Danish National Election Study (DNES)	1971	Centre for survey and Survey/Register data (CSSR)	https://api.datacite.org/doi?query=%22Danish+Elect ion+Study%22&resource-type-id=dataset&page[size]=1000	26
Estonian National Election Study (ENES)	2003	Estonian National Election Study (ENES)	https://api.datacite.org/doi?resource-type-id=dataset&query=Estonian+Election+Survey&page[size]=1000	1
Finnish National Election Study (FNES)	2003	Finish Social Science Data Archive (FSD)	https://api.datacite.org/doi?query=titles.title%3A+%2 2Finnish+National+Election+Study%22&resource-type-id=dataset&page[size]=1000	3
French Election Study (FES)	1958	French Data Archive For Social Sciences (CDSP)	https://api.datacite.org/doi?query=titles.title%3A+%2 2French+Election+Study%22&resource-type-id=dataset&page[size]=1000	14
German Longitudinal Election Study (GLES)	1949	GESIS - Leibniz-Institut für Sozialwissenschaften	https://api.datacite.org/doi?query=titles.title%3A+%2 8%22German+Election+Study%22+OR+%22GLES %22%29&resource-type-id=dataset&page[size]=1000	426
British Election Study (BES)	1963	UK Data Service	https://api.datacite.org/doi?resource-type-id=dataset&query=titles.title%3A+%22British+Electio	65

			n+Study%22&page[size]=1000	
Hellenic National Election Studies (ELNES)	2009	Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research (ICPSR)	https://api.datacite.org/doi?resource-type-id=dataset&query=titles.title%3A+%28Hellenic+Voter+Study%29+OR+titles.title%3A+%28Greek+Elections+2015%29&page[size]=1000	28
Hungarian Election Study	1996	TÁRKI Social Research Institute (TARKI)	https://api.datacite.org/doi?resource-type-id=dataset&query=titles.title%3A+%28Hungar*+Election%29+AND+titles.title%3A+%28Survey+OR+Study+OR+Studies%29&page[size]=1000	4
Icelandic National Election Study (ICENES)	1983	Social Science Research Institute (SSRI)		0
Irish National Election Study (INES)	2002	Irish Social Science Data Archive (ISSDA)	https://api.datacite.org/doi?query=titles.title%3A+%22Irish+General+Election%22+OR+titles.title%3A+%28%22Irish+Election+Studies%22%29&page[size]=1000	4
Israel National Election Studies (INES)	1969	Israel National Election Studies (INES)	https://api.datacite.org/doi?resource-type-id=dataset&query=container.title%3A+%22Israeli+Election+Study+Series%22&page[size]=1000	25
Italian National Election Study (ITANES)	1968	Italian National Election Study (ITANES)		0
Japanese Election Study (JES)	1983	Social Science Japan Data Archive (SSJDA)	https://api.datacite.org/doi?resource-type-id=dataset&query=titles.title%3A+%22Japanese+Election%22+AND+titles.title%3A+%22Study%22&page[size]=1000	5
Lithuanian National Election Study (LNES)	2012	Lietuvos HSM duomenų archyvas (LiDA)		0
Dutch Parliamentary Election Studies (DPES)	1971	Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS)	https://api.datacite.org/doi?query=titles.title%3A+Dutch+Parliamentary+Election+Studies&resource-type-id=dataset&page[size]=1000	41
New Zealand Election Study (NZES)	1990	New Zealand Election Study (NZES)	https://api.datacite.org/doi?resource-type-id=dataset&query=titles.title%3A+%28New+Zealand+Election%29+AND+publisher%3A+%22ADA+Dataverse%22&page[size]=1000	14
Norwegian National Election Studies (NNES)	1957	Norwegian Centre for Research Data (NSD)	https://api.datacite.org/doi?resource-type-id=dataset&query=titles.title%3A+Norwegian+Election+Study&page[size]=1000	28
Polish National Election Study (PGSW)	1997	GESIS - Leibniz-Institut für Sozialwissenschaften	https://api.datacite.org/doi?resource-type-id=dataset&query=titles.title%3A+%22Polish+National+Election+Study%22&page[size]=1000	4

Portuguese Election Study (CEP)	2002	Production and Archive of Social Science Data (PASSDA)	https://api.datacite.org/does?resource-type-id=dataset&query=titles.title%3A+%22Portuguese+Election+Study%22&page[size]=1000	1
Spanish Election Studies (CIS)	1977	Centro de Investigacione Sociológicas (CIS)		0
Swedish National Election Studies (SNES)	1960	Swedish National Data Archive (SND)	https://api.datacite.org/does?resource-type-id=dataset&query=titles.title%3A+%22Swedish+Elect ion+Study%22&page[size]=1000	44
Swiss Election Study (Selects)	1971	FORS	https://api.datacite.org/does?resource-type-id=dataset&query=titles.title%3A+%28%22Selects%22+OR+%22Swiss+Election+Study%22%29+AND+publisher%3A+FORS&page[size]=1000	11
American National Election Study (ANES)	1948	American National Election Study (ANES)	https://api.datacite.org/does?query=container.title%3A+%22American+National+Election+Study+%28ANES%29+Series%22&page[size]=1000	239

APPENDIX C. Set of regular expressions used to clean the abstracts of publications

Some strings had to be treated, such as missing ("NULL", "NA", "", and "JSTOR is a not-for-profit-service."). In Crossref abstracts, jats tags were replaced (see regular expressions below).

```
str_replace_all(.x, "^NULL$", as.character(NA))
str_replace_all(.x, "^NA$", as.character(NA))
str_replace_all(.x, "^$", as.character(NA))
str_replace_all(.x, "^JSTOR is a not-for-profit service.*$",
as.character(NA))
Crossref: str_replace_all(abstract_crossref, "<jats.*?>", "")
Crossref: str_replace_all(abstract_crossref, "</jats.*?>", "")
```

APPENDIX D. Description of the fields retrieved during the harvesting of publications from various sources.

On the tabular export of the list of publications, as described in subsection 3.2, all information returned from Crossref is stored in columns called "crossref_", all information from Scopus has the prefix "scopus_". Columns with the prefix "meta_" come from the data provided by the authors of the meta analyses.

Here follows a description of the properties merged/created for the majority of the fields for all publications:

- *doi*: Unique identifier for the publications (*DOI* for Crossref, *prism:doi* for Scopus)
- *authors*: Authors according to Scopus, if Scopus was missing according to Crossref, and finally from the data provided by the authors of the meta analyses (not possible for new publications).
 - Authors are parsed from Crossref as follows: "*family, given*" -> if *given* is not available, only "*family*" -> if "*family*" is not available use "*name*".
 - Authors are parsed from Scopus as "*family, given*".
 - Multiple authors are concatenated by "; "
- *date*: Crossref date for published in print (*published.print*) was preferred, then *issued* (Crossref), *prism:coverDate* (Scopus), and finally information from meta analyses
- *title*: Crossref *title*, if the title in Crossref is split into *title* and *subtitle*, the two are combined. If still missing, then Scopus, then meta analyses.
- *publication*: Crossref (*container.title*), then Scopus (*prism:publicationName*), else data from meta analyses
- *type*: Crossref (*type*) and then Scopus (*subtypeDescription*)
- *abstract*: Abstracts were retrieved from Semantic Scholar, if still missing from Scopus, then from Crossref, and finally from the description field of the meta analyses data
- *fields*: *subject_areas* from Crossref and *subject-areas* from Scopus are concatenated by "; " (duplicates might be present)
- *keywords*: *authkeywords* and *idxterms* from Scopus are merged (concatenated by "; ") (duplicates might be present)
- *citations*: The number of citations for the publications comes from Crossref (*is-referenced-by-count*) or Scopus (*citedby-count*), The higher number was chosen if both data sources reported the number of citations.
- *volume*: The volume as reported in Crossref (*volume*), if missing from Crossref, then from Scopus (*prism:volume*)
- *issue*: The issue as reported in Crossref (*issue*), if missing from Crossref, then from Scopus (*prism:issueldentifier*)
- *pages*: The pages as reported in Crossref (*page*), if missing from Crossref, then from Scopus (*prism:pageRange*)

- *publisher*: The publisher as reported in Crossref (*publisher*), if missing from Crossref, then from Scopus (*dc:publisher*)

More, potentially interesting, fields that were included:

- *crossref_language*: Crossref reports the language (*language*)
- *scopus_openaccess*, *scopus_openaccessFlag*: Scopus reports if an article is open access (*openaccess*, *openaccessFlag*)
- *crossref_url*: Crossref reports an URL. However, this is just the (old) URL to the DOI resolver. We could generate it ourselves as [https://doi.org/\[DOI\]](https://doi.org/[DOI])
- *crossref_alternative.id*, *scopus_eid*, *scopus_dc_identifier*, *scopus_pii*: Alternative IDs

Matching fields from various APIs (Crossref, SemanticScholar, Microsoft Academic, and Scopus). Current version of the Electoral Studies Knowledge Graph uses metadata from Crossref and Scopus.

Main column in used data	Crossref column in used data	Crossref REST API	SchemanticScholar API	Microsoft Academic	Scopus
authors	crossref_authors	author (not all elements, such as "given" or "family" are always available)	authors	AA.AuN	authors
date	crossref_published .print, crossref_issued	published-print, issued	year	Y	prism:coverDate
title	crossref_title	title [if also <i>subtitle</i> exists, concatenate as "title: subtitle"]	title	DN	dc:title
publication	crossref_container. title	container-title	venue	VFN	prism:publicationName
type	crossref_type	type	NA	Pt	
abstract	crossref_abstract	abstract	abstract	NA	abstract
fields	crossref_subject_areas	subject	fieldsOfStudy	F.FN	subject-areas
keywords	NA	NA	topics	NA	authkeywords, idxterms
citations	crossref_citedby_count	is-referenced-by-count	[one would have to count the entries under "citations"]	CC	citedby-count
volume	crossref_volume	volume	NA	V	prism:volume
issue	crossref_issue	journal-issue/issue	NA	I	prism:issueIdentifier

					r
pages	crossref_page	page	NA	FP, LP (first and last page, connect with "-")	prism:pageRange
publisher	crossref_publisher	publisher	NA	PB	dc:publisher/NA
NA	crossref_url	URL	NA	NA	NA
NA	crossref_language	language	NA	NA	language
NA	crossref_alternative.id	alternative-id	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	reference	references	NA	bibliography
NA	NA	NA	citations	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	is_open_access	NA	openaccess, openaccessFlag

Types of Publications

SSHOC Typology	Combined Column: type	Column: crossref_type	Column: scopus_subtypeDescription
Journal article	journal-article; Article; Article in Press	journal-article	Article; Article in Press
Book chapter	book-chapter; Chapter	book-chapter	Chapter
Monograph	monograph	monograph	
Edited Volume	book	book	
Working Paper/Pre-Print			
Conference paper	proceedings-article; Conference Paper	proceedings-article	Conference Paper
Thesis	dissertation	dissertation	
Report	report	report	
Other	book-part; dataset; other; posted-content; reference-book; reference-entry; Book; Editorial; Erratum; Letter; Note; Review; Short Survey	book-part; dataset; other; posted-content; reference-book; reference-entry	Book; Editorial; Erratum; Letter; Note; Review; Short Survey

APPENDIX E. Electoral Studies Knowledge Graph Statistics

Here are the number of classes and properties for the graph <https://sshoc.poolparty.biz/ElectoralStudies/>.

Class	Count of entities/resources
https://sshoc.poolparty.biz/SSHOC/Author	5303
https://sshoc.poolparty.biz/SSHOC/Keyword	4669
https://sshoc.poolparty.biz/SSHOC/Publication	3865
https://sshoc.poolparty.biz/SSHOC/PublicationName	1422
https://sshoc.poolparty.biz/SSHOC/Dataset	1081
https://sshoc.poolparty.biz/SSHOC/Publisher	347
https://sshoc.poolparty.biz/SSHOC/Field	175

Property	Count of entities/resources
https://sshoc.poolparty.biz/SSHOC/hasConcept	22470
dcterms:title	17246
rdf:type	16862
https://sshoc.poolparty.biz/SSHOC/hasAuthor	10448
schema:image	10249
https://sshoc.poolparty.biz/SSHOC/keyword	8844
https://sshoc.poolparty.biz/SSHOC/field	5809
https://sshoc.poolparty.biz/SSHOC/doi	4946
https://sshoc.poolparty.biz/SSHOC/url	4946
dcterms:type	4943
https://sshoc.poolparty.biz/SSHOC/publicationYear	4892

https://sshoc.poolparty.biz/SSHOC/abstract	4101
https://sshoc.poolparty.biz/SSHOC/citations	3862
https://sshoc.poolparty.biz/SSHOC/publisher	3856
https://sshoc.poolparty.biz/SSHOC/publication	3829
https://sshoc.poolparty.biz/SSHOC/publicationDate	3811
https://sshoc.poolparty.biz/SSHOC/pages	3581
https://sshoc.poolparty.biz/SSHOC/volume	3092
https://sshoc.poolparty.biz/SSHOC/issue	2894
https://sshoc.poolparty.biz/SSHOC/mentionsCountry	2215
https://sshoc.poolparty.biz/SSHOC/group	1112
dcterms:alternative	691
https://sshoc.poolparty.biz/SSHOC/source	343
https://sshoc.poolparty.biz/SSHOC/usesDataSource	123
skos:notation	90

APPENDIX G. A snippet from the defined SHACL shapes used to validate the produced KG.

```
@prefix rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#> .
@prefix rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> .
@prefix schema: <http://schema.org/> .
@prefix sh: <http://www.w3.org/ns/shacl#> .
@prefix xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> .
@prefix dct: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/> .
@prefix swc: <http://semantic-web.com/shapes/> .
@prefix sshoc: <https://sshoc.poolparty.biz/SSHOC/> .
```

```
sshoc:ResourceShape
  a sh:NodeShape ;
  sh:targetClass sshoc:Dataset, sshoc:Publication ;
  sh:closed false ;
  sh:property [
    sh:path dct:title ;
    sh:minCount 1 ;
    sh:datatype rdf:langString ;
    sh:uniqueLang true ;
    sh:severity sh:Warning ;
  ],
  [
    sh:path dct:type ;
    sh:minCount 1 ;
    sh:maxCount 1 ;
    sh:severity sh:Warning ;
  ],
  [
    sh:path sshoc:doi ;
    sh:minCount 1 ;
    sh:maxCount 1 ;
    sh:severity sh:Warning ;
  ],
  [
    sh:path sshoc:publicationYear ;
    sh:minCount 1 ;
    sh:maxCount 1 ;
    sh:severity sh:Warning ;
  ],
  [
    sh:path sshoc:hasAuthor ;
```

```
    sh:minCount 1 ;
    sh:severity sh:Info ;
    sh:node sshoc:AuthorShape ;
  ],
  [
    sh:path sshoc:hasConcept ;
    sh:minCount 1 ;
    sh:severity sh:Info ;
  ],
  [
    sh:path sshoc:url ;
    sh:minCount 1 ;
    sh:severity sh:Info ;
    swc:hasPattern swc:UriPattern ;
  ],
  [
    sh:path sshoc:hasAuthor ;
    sh:minCount 1 ;
    sh:severity sh:Info ;
  ],
  [
    sh:path dct:title ;
    sh:qualifiedValueShape [ sh:languageIn ("en") ] ;
    sh:message "There should be exactly one dct:title in language 'en'." ;
    sh:severity sh:Violation ;
    sh:qualifiedMinCount 1 ;
    sh:qualifiedMaxCount 1 ;
  ],
  [
    sh:path sshoc:abstract ;
    sh:qualifiedValueShape [ sh:languageIn ("en") ] ;
    sh:message "There should be exactly one sshoc:abstract in language 'en'." ;
    sh:severity sh:Violation ;
    sh:qualifiedMinCount 1 ;
    sh:qualifiedMaxCount 1 ;
  ] .
```